
EUROSCITIZEN COST ACTION - VIRTUAL NETWORKING SUPPORT GRANT 2021

Instructions to set up **Zoom events**

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These are some suggestions for setting up zoom events. These might vary depending on the needs and aims of the specific event, please confirm with the meeting organisers:

While setting up the specific meeting/webinar:

Topic:

The exact topic that was advertised by the meeting organisers

Time Zone:

Make sure you select the appropriate time zone for the event. This might be different from your time zone.

Registration:

Discuss this with the organisers. While this poses an extra barrier to the audience, it might be a good idea in case the organisers are concerned about potential zoom bombing.

Passcode:

Instead of the random number generated by zoom, you could change this to something easier, e.g. the date of the event, or the name of the event/organiser.

Waiting room:

This will allow you to let participants enter when you are ready. It will also serve as an additional security check to prevent unauthorised participants and disruptions. Additionally, once the event is concluded, participants who have not yet disconnected can be moved to the waiting room to allow the organisers/hosts to debrief in privacy.

Mute participants upon entry:

A good practise that will ensure that latecomers do not disturb the proceedings.

Record the meetings:

Please discuss with the organisers the need to record the meeting and about the location of the recording. It is not advisable to record to your computer but rather to record to the cloud.

Setting up alternative hosts:

It is advisable to have some alternative hosts who can start the meeting in case of technical difficulties.

Other settings to be considered:

The following are available in the “Settings” tab.

Chat:

Usually, any participants can save the chat from the meeting. However, if the meeting organisers do not want this option, make sure that it is unticked.

Sound notification when someone joins or leaves.

Ensure that this option is either unticked for everyone or ticked only for the hosts/co-hosts as it can be very distracting to participants.

Meeting/Webinar Polls/Quizzes/Surveys:

Tick if the meeting hosts would want to have participants interact in this way. If this is ticked, it is then the moderator’s responsibility to make sure that the polls/quizzes/surveys are uploaded to the zoom meeting/webinar preferably before it starts.

Screen Sharing:

- It is advisable to have only the host be able to share the screen to prevent distractions.
- If during the event, a participant needs to share their screen, they can be temporarily made a co-host, or given the ability to share their screen.
- Additionally, please make sure that the option “Who can start sharing when someone else is sharing?” is set to Host only

Non-verbal feedback and meeting reactions:

Enable these to allow participants to interact without needing to turn on their microphones.

Allow participants to rename themselves:

This is particularly useful in case you want to know their institutional affiliation or their role in that particular meeting. Additionally, having the role displayed allows participants to target their questions in chat.

Breakout rooms:

Enable them by default. Please discuss the number of rooms, number of participants, random/intentional sorting with the organisers.

Closed captioning:

To make the meeting more accessible it could be advisable to enable closed captioning. However, please note that this is done by an AI and might not be accurate in all languages and for all accents. Additionally, closed captions can be distracting to some participants, and they must be clearly told how to turn them off for themselves.

Allowing live streaming:

Please discuss with organisers about the need for this feature

Trolls and Zoombombing:

It is possible that virtual/hybrid events are affected by uninvited and disruptive people. It is important therefore to try and avoid Zoombombers/trolls and know how to deal with them if necessary.

Avoiding Zoombombing/Trolls:

- Be careful while sharing the zoom link. If possible, share it only with participants who have registered for the event.
- Avoid sharing the link on social media. You could share the link to the event registration page instead.
- Set up a waiting room and be selective while admitting people after the event has started.

Dealing with Zoombombing/Trolls:

- Take over screen sharing: If the Zoombomber/Troll starts sharing undesirable material on the screen, immediately share your screen instead. Please refer to tips on setting up screen sharing in the previous section.
- Mute the Zoombomber/Troll: Immediately mute the disruptive person. You can do this by clicking the 'More' option next to their name in the participant list or in the top left-hand corner of their picture.
- Kick the Zoombomber/Troll out of the event: Click 'Remove' next to the name of the person. Keep an eye on the waiting room to make sure you do not let them re-enter the event.

Additional useful tips can be found in the [Zoom Help Center](#)